

A study of Correlation of Transverse Cerebellar Diameter with Gestational Age in the Normal & Growth Restricted Fetuses in Western Uttar Pradesh

Mukesh Bansal, Alpana Bansal*, Shilpi Jain**, Satyam Khare**, Rashmi Ghai**

Department of Anatomy, Saraswathi Institute of Medical Sciences, Anwarpur, Hapur, *Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Rama Medical College Hospital & Research Center, Hapur, **Department of Anatomy, Subharti Medical College, Meerut.

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ABSTRACT:

Transverse Cerebellar Diameter (TCD) is a more accurate & better predictor of gestational age in normal as well as in IUGR fetuses. In intra uterine growth restricted (IUGR) Fetuses, the transverse cerebellar diameter does not get affected due to insufficiency of fetal circulation and so can be used as an unbiased measurement of gestational age (GA). It withstands deformation by external pressure because Cerebellum is the largest part of hind brain which lies in the posterior cranial fossa, surrounded by the dense petrous ridges and the occipital bone. The cerebellum is easily visualized sonographically. The aim of this study was to establish 'Correlation between TCD & GA in Normal & IUGR fetuses'.

The study group comprised of 650 cases. Women having pregnancy between 14 to 40 weeks were considered for Ultrasound Examination. Patients who had any complication of pregnancy were not included in the study. During 14 to 26 weeks of gestation- transverse cerebellar diameter in mm was found equivalent to gestation age of fetus. The Karl Pearson correlation coefficient between gestational age & transverse cerebellar diameter was found to be 0.972305. p-value is < 0.001 which was highly significant. In IUGR Fetuses, the value of measurement of Transverse Cerebellar Diameter was less than the normally grown fetuses. The mean difference was 1.065 from the expected mean for normally grown fetuses. p-value was $p < 0.01$ i.e. statistically significant. In the normal & IUGR Fetuses the Transverse Cerebellar Diameter increases with advancing age. Linear relationship of TCD is observed with GA. This study shows highly significant correlation between Transverse Cerebellar Diameter & Gestation age in normal & IUGR fetuses.

KEY WORDS: Fetuses, Gestational Age (GA), Intra uterine growth restricted (IUGR), Transverse Cerebellar Diameter (TCD), Ultrasound/ Ultrasonography (USG).

INTRODUCTION:

Objective knowledge of the expected date of delivery (EDD) is essential in management of all pregnancies particularly the method of delivery, management of high risk pregnancies, elective planned induction of labour and elective caesarean for previous caesarean section deliveries.

The obstetrician calculates the EDD as 280 days or 40 weeks from the first day of the LMP. In women with regular 28-day menstrual periods, the

method is fairly accurate, but if cycles are irregular, substantial miscalculations may be made. Hence, the day of delivery is not always easy to determine. Higher perinatal mortality has been reported in patients whose expected date of confinement is not known as compared to those in whom it is known.^[1]

Determination of fetal age and growth is crucial in planning pregnancy management, especially for low-birth-weight infants. Ultrasound screened and managed pregnancies with low-birth-weight babies reduce the mortality rate by 60%. Fetal age and growth are assessed by crown-rump length during the 5th to 10th weeks of gestation. After that, a combination of measurement-including the Biparietal (BPD) of the skull, femur length, and abdominal circumference are

Corresponding Author: Dr. Mukesh Bansal, Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Saraswati Institute of Medical Sciences, Anwarpur, Hapur, UP (India).
Phone No.: +91 7599342770
E-mail : bansalmukesh4@gmail.com

used. Multiple measures of these parameters over time improve the ability to determine the extent of fetal growth.^[1]

These parameters are limited for clinical usefulness in establishing gestational age in late pregnancy or in assessing fetal growth in uncertain dated pregnancies. This was explained by the increasing biologic variability in advancing gestational age. To determine the abnormal fetal growth, serial ultrasonographic evaluation in the third trimester is required for appropriate fetal surveillance and intervention.^[2]

The evaluation of the posterior fossa of the fetal cranium has been accepted as part of the routine obstetric ultrasonographic (USG) examination. The size of the cerebellum or transverse cerebellar diameter (TCD) is important because it is a useful biometric parameter in estimating gestational age (GA) in the second trimester.^[3] Indeed, in some cases with dolichocephaly or brachycephaly, TCD may be a more reliable predictor than biparietal diameter since the posterior fossa is not affected by external pressure including fetal malposition, breech presentation or oligohydramnios, which may induce distortion of the fetal head.^[3] TCD can reliably be used in cases of femur achondroplasia where femur length is unreliable. Because TCD seems unaffected by intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR),^[4,5] measuring TCD is especially advantageous when IUGR is suspected or when GA is uncertain.

IUGR is caused mostly by asphyxia or reduced utero-placental blood flow. In acute asphyxia, cerebellar blood flow remains unchanged as a consequence of redistribution of cardiac output. The blood flow shifts mainly to the central parts including brain, heart and adrenal glands. In humans, cerebellar growth may be least affected by IUGR, therefore TCD measurement is mostly accurate in the prediction of gestational age.^[6]

The cerebellum, the largest part of the hind brain, is surrounded laterally by the dense petrous ridges and inferiorly by the occipital bone, which is aligned perpendicular to the plane of maximum extrinsic compression. Thus, the cerebellum and posterior fossa should theoretically be able to withstand deformation by extrinsic pressure better than the parietal bones.^[7]

The cerebellum represents an area of the brain that is easily visualized sonographically. Measurement and demonstration of fetal cerebellum is a new and unique parameter of fetal brain growth. It is also useful

in assessing gestational age. The fetal cerebellum can be visualized sonographically as early as 12 weeks of gestation. From the second trimester, it grows rapidly with a linear relationship pattern correlating with gestational age.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The present study was conducted in the Department of Anatomy, Subharti Medical College Meerut, in collaboration with the Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Associated Chhatrapati Shivaji Subharti Hospital, Meerut. Ethical clearance was obtained from Institutional Ethical Committee.

Source of data:

The study was carried out on pregnant women attending the clinic for routine ultrasound examination and seeking antenatal care between 14 to 40 weeks of pregnancy. A total of 650 women were examined for this study. Out of 650 cases Trans Cerebellar Diameter could be obtained in 638 cases, whereas 12 cases were excluded due to fetal anomaly & fetal malposition. Out of 638 cases, 59 fetuses were IUGR fetuses.

Method of study:

The USG estimation of gestational age was done by transcerebellar diameter, bi-parietal diameter, head circumference, abdominal circumference, femur length & humerus length in normal and IUGR pregnancies. Software used for statistical analysis were SPSS V-19 (Statistical Package for the Social Science). Correlation coefficient, unpaired 't' test and p-value were calculated. Linear regression analysis and ANOVAs single factor to test the regression line was used to estimate the predicted values and their 95% confidence intervals for each gestational age.

Inclusion criteria:

- (a) Normal singleton pregnancies of 14 and 40 weeks gestation with known last menstrual period;
- (b) Clinically suspected intrauterine growth retardation.

Exclusion criteria:

- (a) Congenital malformations; (b) Multiple pregnancies.

The Equipment:

All measurements were made by scanning the patients using WIPRO GE LOGIQ ALPHA-100 PRO & other USG machine present in Obstetrics and Gynecology Department of Subharti Medical College,

diameter; Figure 1).

Figure 1: Showing measurement of Transverse Cerebellar Diameter.

Meerut using 3.5-5 MHz frequency convex trans abdominal and 5-10 MHz frequency trans-vaginal transducers.

Statistical formula: Correlation coefficient (r)

$$r = \frac{\text{cov}(x, y)}{\sigma_{x, xy}} = \frac{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Techniques of Measurement:

The transverse cerebellar diameter is mainly measured in Trans cerebellar plane. The measurement of TCD was obtained by placing electronic calipers at outer to outer margins of cerebellum. The landmarks of thalami, cavum, septum pellucidum and third ventricle were identified thereby slightly rotating the transducer below the thalamic plane. The posterior fossa was revealed with the characteristic butterfly like appearance of cerebellum. In all cases cerebellum was seen as two lobules on either side of midline in the posterior cranial fossa. The measurement is obtained by positioning the calipers on the outer margins of the two hemispheres (TCD or transverse cerebellum).

RESULTS:

The results of this study are as follows:

1. Age group distribution & their percentage during different weeks of gestation shows that our study included cases of all weeks in reasonable number, which gave strength to the authenticity of result

[Table 1].

2. Mean & Standard Deviation for each week of gestation shows that TCD in mm is equal to Gestational Age in weeks during 14-24 weeks [Table 2].
3. The Karl Pearson Correlation coefficient between TCD & GA was 0.9388.
4. Pair wise comparison between TCD and Gestational Age shows probable value of 't' (unpaired) as 0.0000 and p value being <0.0001 i.e. highly significant.
5. Regression analysis was done for Trans-Cerebellar Diameter and Gestation Age. Formula obtained was $X = 0.7118Y + 6.8091$ (X = Gestation Age; Y = Trans Cerebellar Diameter).
6. Graphical representation of collected data between Gestation Age and Transverse Cerebellar Diameter shows linear relationship [Graph 1].
7. In IUGR cases: Mean & Standard Deviation of TCD in mm were 28 ± 1.87 for 25-28 weeks, 34.47 ± 1.68 for 29-32 weeks, 40.54 ± 3.01 for 33-36 weeks and 45 ± 0.82 for 37-40 weeks. The correlation coefficient between TCD & GA was 0.9686. One way ANOVA- F shows that p value <0.01 (which was statistically significant).

DISCUSSION:

Knowledge of normal embryology and its corresponding ultrasound images, the expertise of the operators and the availability of high-resolution equipment are essential for an adequate evaluation of the fetus.

We compared transverse cerebellar diameter and gestation age in our study and found that sonographic evaluation of cerebellar growth reveals a linear relationship. Correlation coefficient between TCD and gestational age was 0.9388 with $p < 0.001$ which is statistically significant, similar to the findings of Meyer WJ et al (1993)^[8], Goel P. et al (2010).^[9]

Reece et al^[4] in their study found that TCD from 15th to 24th week of gestation in millimeters is equivalent to the gestation age in weeks. However, after 24 weeks the TCD in millimeters exceeds gestational age in weeks. In our Study, measurement of TCD in mm up to 24 weeks is equal to gestational age. The results of our prospective study provides normative data of fetal cerebellar growth throughout gestation.

The inability to ascertain gestational age by ultrasound parameters in the third trimester has proved

Table 1: Showing age group distribution & their percentage during different weeks of gestation.

S.No.	Gestation weeks	Number of Patient observed	Percentage
1	14	8	1.38%
2	15	11	1.90%
3	16	23	3.97%
4	17	25	4.32%
5	18	24	4.01%
6	19	17	2.42%
7	20	36	4.91%
8	21	22	3.91%
9	22	14	2.41%
10	23	21	3.63%
11	24	21	3.63%
12	25	21	3.63%
13	26	20	3.58%
14	27	19	3.12%
15	28	29	5.01%
16	29	30	5.12%
17	30	50	8.64%
18	31	39	5.02%
19	32	37	4.07%
20	33	42	7.22%
21	34	28	4.82%
22	35	18	2.51%
23	36	16	2.34%
24	37	04	0.69%
25	38	04	0.69%

Table 2: Showing Mean & Standard Deviation for each week of gestation.

S.No.	Gestation Age (weeks)	Mean of TCD (mm)	S.D.
1	14	14.02	0.15
2	15	15.12	0.21
3	16	16.14	0.38
4	17	17.03	0.35
5	18	18.18	0.54
6	19	19.42	0.37
7	20	20.23	0.47
8	21	21.67	0.74
9	22	22.69	0.84
10	23	23.78	0.73
11	24	24.85	0.9
12	25	26.14	0.45
13	26	27.68	1.47
14	27	29.02	0.82
15	28	30.09	0.83
16	29	31.85	0.8
17	30	33.71	1.53
18	31	35.52	1.62
19	32	37.07	2.07
20	33	38.51	2.93
21	34	41.75	3.43
22	35	43.57	2.7
23	36	44.02	1.02
24	37	46.47	0.97
25	38	48.63	1.23

to be a major cause of undiagnosed fetal IUGR. Fetal transverse cerebellar diameter is independent of the fetal head shape and can be measured in most fetuses. This was found to be a reliable predictor of gestational age in the third trimester.^[9] In general, IUGR is usually suspected from a discrepancy between uterine size and

gestational age. So, the predictive accuracy of clinical parameters for diagnosis of IUGR is poor. The diagnosis needs to be more precise and objective measure are required to assess the fetus with suspected IUGR.

When IUGR is suspected, in order to better

Line Graph 1: Showing linear relationship between Gestational Age & Transverse Cerebellar Diameter

evaluate fetal biometry, the TCD should also be used. Cabbad et al^[10] and associates found that 22 out of 23 asymmetrically growth-impaired fetuses had a TCD lower than expected but within the normal range suggesting this measurement was useful for estimation of gestational age in these cases. Our ultrasonographic study of 59 intrauterine growth retarded fetuses shows that the growth of the TCD is unaffected by intrauterine growth retardation. Thus the sonographic measurement of TCD may serve as an independent and reliable parameter of GA against which potential deviations of growth may be compared.

CONCLUSION:

On the basis of the observations made during study, the following conclusions were drawn:

A normogram is made comparing transverse cerebellar diameter with gestational age. Line diagram plotted between gestational age and Transverse Cerebellar Diameter shows linear relation. Gestational age (in weeks), mean of TCD (in mm) and Standard Deviation was calculated which showed linear growth of all variables along with gestational age. TCD measured in mm was almost equal to Gestational age up to 24 weeks. Correlation coefficient between TCD and GA was 0.9388. The Correlation coefficient was statistically significant. p value < 0.0001 (highly significant). Regression analysis shows a strongly significant relationship.

Parameter which correlated most with Gestational age is Transverse Cerebellum Diameter. In the normally developing fetus, the TCD increases with advancing gestational age. Transverse cerebellum diameter is a good marker for gestational age and can be used in cases that are not sure about the dates. The value of TCD was less in IUGR fetuses than in normal growth fetuses, but the difference was within normal

limits indicating that there is significant co-relation between TCD and GA in both IUGR and normal fetuses.

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